

ROLE OF STRESS IN DIABETES MELLITUS AND ITS MANAGEMENT THROUGH AYURVEDA

¹*Dr. Satyapal Sharma, ²Dr. Chandan Singh

¹Assistant Professor, Deptt. of Dravyaguna, Shri Dhanwantri Ayurveda Medical College and Research Centre, Mathura.

²Professor and HOD, Deptt. of Dravyaguna, Post Graduate Institute of Ayurveda Studies and Research, DSRRAU, Jodhpur.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Satyapal Sharma

Assistant Professor, Deptt. of
Dravyaguna, Shri Dhanwantri
Ayurveda Medical College and
Research Centre, Mathura.

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ABSTRACT

Stress means failure of an organism to respond appropriately to emotional or physical threats. Stress has long been suspected to be having a role in the development of Diabetes mellitus. Stress stimulates the release of various hormones like catecholamine which can result in elevated glucose level. This happens as an adaptive mechanism for energy mobilization in relation with fight or flight response. In *Ayurvedic* classics a detailed description is there about *Prameha* one among the *Maharoga*. The management of stress has a significant role in the management strategy of Diabetes, the highly prevalent life style disorder and also endocrinal disorder. The stressful life events constitute the etiopathogenesis of DM. *Acharya* opine that the administrations of medicines are not the only way to manage disease but life style modification is also necessary to minimize it. Though various stress management program including *yoga*, *Sadvritta* methods mentioned by *Acharya*

Charaka are beneficial, herbs mentioned in Ayurveda also help to reduce the stress and stress hormones which is related to blood glucose level. Present paper aims at putting forward *yoga*, *sadvritta* methods and some herbs which can be used to eliminate or reduce stress and prevent the DM.

KEYWORDS: Stress, Diabetes Mellitus, Yoga, Sadvritta, Herbs.

INTRODUCTION

Term Stress derived from the Latin word “stringere” mean hardship, strain, adversity. In medical terms stress refers to a wide range of strong external stimuli, both physiological and psychological, which can cause a physiological response called the ‘general adaptation syndrome’. Thus the disruption of homeostasis through physiological, anatomical or mental stimuli is known as stress.^[1]

Anxiety, antagonism, exhaustion, frustration, distress, despair, overwork, pre-menstrual tension, over-focusing, confusion, mourning, and fear could all come together in a general broad term, “stress”.

Stress is an essential part of everybody life. Without stress, there will be no progress. Thus stress, should be taken up as a challenges to perform better in life.

So, stress management become necessary only when there is negative stress.

Diabetes mellitus is a group of metabolic diseases characterized by high blood sugar (glucose) levels that result from defects in insulin secretion, or its action, or both. Normally, blood glucose levels are tightly controlled by insulin, a hormone produced by the pancreas. In patients with diabetes, the absence of insufficient production of or lack of response to insulin causes hyperglycemia.

There are two major types of diabetes, called type 1 and type 2.

Type 1 diabetes was also formerly called insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM), or juvenile onset diabetes mellitus. In type 1 diabetes, the pancreas undergoes an autoimmune attack by the body itself, and is rendered incapable of making insulin. In persons with type 1 diabetes, the beta cells of the pancreas, which are responsible for insulin production, are attacked by the misdirected immune system.^[2]

Type 2 diabetes was also previously referred to as non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM), or adult onset diabetes mellitus (AODM). In type 2 diabetes, patients can still produce insulin, but do so relatively inadequately for their body's needs, Type 2 diabetes was also previously referred to as non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM), or adult onset diabetes mellitus (AODM). In type 2 diabetes, patients can still produce insulin, but do so relatively inadequately for their body's needs.

Other types of diabetes is blood sugar elevation during pregnancy is called gestational diabetes.

Relation between stress and diabetes

Stress may sometimes unmask diabetes, by causing blood glucose levels to rise. This is often seen after a heart attack or stroke, where raised blood sugar levels may be encountered for the first time. Stress hormones that are designed to deal with short-term danger stay turned on for a long time. As a result, long-term stress can cause long-term high blood sugar levels. Many long-term sources of stress are mental. Physical stress, such as illness or injury, causes higher blood sugar levels in people with either type of diabetes. In the fight or flight response, levels of many hormones like catecholamines, cortisol and growth hormone shoot up. Their net effect is to make a lot of stored energy, glucose and fat available to cells. Insulin is not always able to let the extra energy into the cells, so glucose piles up in the blood. These results in increase propensity of various diseases and diabetes may be an outcome of stress, which further sets in a vicious cycle of stress-diabetes relationship.^[3]

Stressful experiences have been implicated in the onset of diabetes in individuals already predisposed to developing the disease. As early as the beginning of the 17th century, the onset of diabetes was linked to “prolonged sorrow” by an English physician.^[4] Since then, a number of research studies have identified stressors such as family losses and workplace stress as factors triggering the onset of diabetes; both type 1 and type 2 (Therlund et al).^[5]

Suggested that negative stressful experiences in the first 2 years of life may increase the risk of developing type 1 diabetes in children. Other factors, such as high family chaos and behavioral problems, were also implicated. Other research has also supported the hypothesis that stressful experiences can lead to increased risk for developing type 1 or type 2 diabetes.^[6]

Pathophysiology of Stress

Following any physical or mental stress there occur two types of reactions.

Homeostatic Mechanism: It attempts to counteract the everyday stress of living. If they are successful, the internal environment maintains normal physiological limits of chemistry, temperature and pressure.

• **General Adaptation Syndrome (GAS):** If a stress is extreme, unusual or long lasting however, the normal mechanisms may not be sufficient. Then, the stress triggers a wide-

ranging set of bodily changes called the stress responses or general adaptation syndrome (GAS).

It has three successive phases

1. Alarm Reaction
2. Resistance Reaction
3. Exhaustion

1. Alarm Reaction

When the threat or stressor is identified or realized, the body's stress response is a state of alarm. During this stage adrenaline will be produced in order to bring about the fight-or-flight response. There is also some activation of the HPA axis, producing cortisol.

2. Resistance

If the stressor persists, it becomes necessary to attempt some means of coping with the stress. Although the body begins to try to adapt to the strains or demands of the environment, the body cannot keep this up indefinitely, so its resources are gradually depleted.

3. Exhaustion

In the final stage in the GAS model, all the body's resources are eventually depleted and the body is unable to maintain normal function. At this point the initial autonomic nervous system symptoms may reappear (sweating, raised heart rate etc.). If stage three is extended, long term damage may result as the capacity of glands, especially the adrenal gland, and the immune system is exhausted and function is impaired resulting in decompensation. The result can manifest itself in obvious illnesses such as ulcers, depression or even cardiovascular problems, along with other mental issues.^[7]

STRESS AND HORMONE

Epinephrine

Most people know epinephrine by its other name adrenaline. This hormone rapidly responds to stress by increasing your heart rate and rushing blood to the muscles and brain. It also spikes your blood sugar level helping convert glycogens to glucose in the liver.

Cortisol

Cortisol is a life sustaining adrenal hormone essential to the maintenance of homeostasis. Called "the stress hormone," cortisol influences, regulates or modulates many of the changes

that occur in the body in response to stress. Higher and more prolonged levels of circulating cortisol (like those associated with chronic stress) have been shown to have negative effects, such as^[8]:

- Impaired cognitive performance
- Dampened thyroid function
- Blood sugar imbalances, such as hyperglycemia
- Lowered immune function

Common manifestation of stress

Digestive system

Stomachache or diarrhea

This happens because stress hormones slow the release of acids and the emptying of the stomach. The same hormones also stimulate the colon, which speeds the passage of its contents. Chronic stress can also lead to continuously high levels of cortisol. This hormone can increase appetite and cause weight gain.

Immune system

Chronic stress tends to dampen the immune system, making one more susceptible to colds and other infections.

Nervous system

If fight-or-flight response never shuts off, stress hormones produce persistent feelings of anxiety, helplessness and impending doom. Oversensitivity to stress has been linked with severe depression, possibly because depressed people have a harder time adapting to the negative effects of cortisol. The byproducts of cortisol act as sedatives, which contribute to the overall feeling of depression.

Cardiovascular system

High levels of cortisol can also raise heart rate and increase blood pressure and blood lipid (cholesterol and triglyceride) levels. Increases risk factors for both heart attacks and stroke.

Other systems

Stress worsens many skin conditions — such as psoriasis, eczema, acne— and can be a trigger for — asthma attacks.^[9]

Relations

A. Stress and free radical

Understanding stress requires knowledge of stress and free radicals. Free radicals are a naturally occurring by product of living and normally handled by the body's immune system. When a person is subjected to too much stress, pollution, and other forms of stressful neglect, the number of free radicals can rise substantially and overcome the body's natural defenses.

They can damage the cell membrane, the lining in the cells and the DNA which controls all the functions of the cells. Similarly they can damage different organs, joints, the heart, the pancreas. If the occurrence is frequent, severe, or longstanding, stress and free radicals can result in severe damage to the body.^[10]

B. Free radical and antioxidants and Vitamin C

An **Antioxidant** is a molecule capable of inhibiting the oxidation of other molecules. Antioxidants terminate the chain reactions by removing free radical intermediates, and inhibit other oxidation reactions. They do this by being oxidized themselves, so antioxidants are often reducing agents such as thiols, ascorbic acid, or polyphenols. In Ayurveda these are grouped as *Vayasthapana Drugs*.

Vitamin C has potent **antioxidant** properties, meaning it is able to reduce damage caused by oxidizing chemicals, such as free radicals. Vitamin C reduces this damage by directly binding to oxidizing chemicals and converting them to less harmful molecules. Reducing oxidative damage can have many benefits for your body, including reducing stress and heart disease.

A.) Free radicals and diabetes

Diabetes mellitus is a common disorder, caused by hyperglycaemia resulting from a deficiency in insulin secretion or action. Animal studies have suggested that reactive radicals contribute to the destruction of pancreatic islet cells in the pathogenesis of insulin dependent diabetes mellitus. Toxic amounts of reactive oxygen intermediates are released by endothelial cells and infiltrating macrophages during islet inflammation. Islet cells are thought to have deficient defense system against free radical attack, making them susceptible to reactive oxygen intermediates, leading to the destruction of the cells. Impaired ascorbic acid metabolism has also been implicated in diabetes. Ascorbate is required for the regeneration of vitamin E *in vivo* and may be oxidized to dehydroascorbic acid, which can disrupt cell structures and act as a neurotoxin. In healthy tissues

dehydroascorbic acid is generally recycled back to ascorbic acid. Increased exposure to high levels of dehydroascorbic acid and low levels of ascorbic acid results in increased susceptibility of the cell to oxidative damage. Other research suggests that high glucose levels in diabetes interfere with ascorbic acid uptake, resulting in low levels of ascorbate in cells.^[11]

B.) Diabetes, Oxidative Stress, and Antioxidants

Increasing evidence in both experimental and clinical studies suggests that oxidative stress plays a major role in the pathogenesis of both types of diabetes mellitus. Free radicals are formed disproportionately in diabetes by glucose oxidation, nonenzymatic glycation of proteins, and the subsequent oxidative degradation of glycated proteins. Abnormally high levels of free radicals and the simultaneous decline of antioxidant defense mechanisms can lead to damage of cellular organelles and enzymes, increased lipid peroxidation, and development of insulin resistance. These consequences of oxidative stress can promote the development of complications of diabetes mellitus.^[12] (A. C. Maritim, R. A. Sanders and J. B. Watkins III 2003).

Management of stress

Stress is unique in the category of disease but is not so easy to eliminate. It has no biological carrier such as germ and virus rather it is the result of how our mind and body function and interact.

Thus the term 'stress management' is more appropriate for dealing with stress and related disorders.

The first principle followed in the Ayurvedic system of medicine is *Swasthyashya Swasthya Rakshanam*, which means to maintain the health of the healthy, followed by *Aturashya Vikara Prashamanancha*, means to cure the diseases if required.^[13]

The term Ayustands for the combination of the body (Sarira), sense organs (Iṅdriya), manas (Ṣattva) and soul (Atma).^[14] The sense organs are the eyes etc, the *Ṣattva* is the mind and the soul is the bearer of the knowledge. All these combined with the virtue of the invisible past actions are designated as Ayu (jiva). So manas is the important and inseparable part of jiva. It plays an important role in all healthy conditions and diseases that generate due to mansikabhavas.

Body (sarira) and mind (manas/sattva) are the two seats of diseases. Therefore diseases are of two types' sharirika and manasika.^[15]

According to Charak, Sharirika and mansika diseases are related and they influence each other.^[16] From this statement psychosomatic phenomenon is accepted in Ayurveda.

In present time many kinds of mental disorders (mansikvyadhiya) generate in society due to changes in life style and increased competitions.

Ayurveda like in any other disease, provides multidimensional approach towards stress management.^[17]

1) **Daiva-vyapashryachikitsa**

In this type of chikitsa mani, mantra, uphaar, prayashchit, swastyayan etc. are described.

2) **Sattvavajayachikitsa**

Deviate the mind (manas/sattva) from unpleasant subjects. Importance of Mental satisfaction is given in it. Dhi, Dhairya, Gyan, Vigyan, Samadhi etc. management method are used to control mind (sattva).

3) **Yukti- vyapashriyachikitsa**

This refers to the rational approach to manage the symptoms and disease. It may again be divided in two parts

Adravyabhootchikitsa

Dravyabhootchikitsa

Adravyabhootchikitsa

In the method of Adavyabhootchikitsa various regimes have been mentioned in the classics of Ayurveda.

Sadvritha

Achararasayana

Dincharya

Ritucharya

Ashtanga yoga

Sadvritta

Sadvritta i.e. code of conduct has an important role in preventing in psychological and psychosomatic disease. Sadvritta deals with the rules concerning mental, spiritual, social hygiene as well as physical hygiene and specially aids in relieving the day to day mental tension and thereby bring about mental harmony along with physical harmony.

Ashtanga yoga

Yoga originated from Sanskrit word “yuj” meaning union between mind, body and spirit. Include ethical discipline, physical postures, breathing control and meditation. The Eight Limbs of Yoga.

1. Yama
2. Niyam
3. Asan
4. Pranayam
5. Pratyahar
6. Dharana
7. Dhyan
8. Samadhi

Virtually everyone can see physical benefits of yoga, and its practice can also give psychological benefits, such as stress reduction and a sense of well-being, and spiritual benefits.

Dravyabhootchikitsa

In this method of management dravyas (drugs) which are mentioned in texts are used according to disease. Various groups of drugs are mentioned in classical Ayurvedic texts which can be used in different stages of stress.

Vayasthapana drugs

“Amrita, Abhaya, Dhatri, Mukta, Shweta, Jivanti, Atirasa, Mandookparni, Sthira, Punarnava”^[18] (Ch.su.4/50)

Drugs which prevents ageing process are known as Vayasthapana. Vayasthapana dravya works like antioxidants which counters the harmful free radicals.

Hridaya Mahakashaya

“Amra, Amratak, Lakuch, Karmarda, Virkshamla, Amlavetas, Kuval, Badar, Dadim, Matulunga.”^[19] (Ch.su.4/10)

Hridya mahakashaya of Charak Samhita enlists fruits which contain amla rasa and rich in vitamic C.

It is very much apparent that Hridya property had a wide spectrum of application in Ayurveda and one important action of amla rasa is beneficial to heart and mind. Thus the role of drugs mentioned in hridya mahakashaya becomes more evident in reducing stress by keeping mind in healthy state.

People who have high levels of vitamin C do not show the expected mental and physical signs of stress when subjected to acute psychological challenges. And they bounce back from stressful situations faster than people with low levels of vitamin C in their blood. Earlier studies showed that vitamin C abolished secretion of cortisol in animals that had been subjected to repeated stress. Cortisol is a hormone released by the adrenal glands in response to stress. The vitamin helps reduce both the physical and psychological effects of stress on people. Treatment with high-dose sustained-release ascorbic acid palliates blood pressure, cortisol, and subjective response to acute psychological stress.^[20] (A randomized controlled trial of high dose ascorbic acid for reduction of blood pressure, cortisol, and subjective responses to psychological stress (Stuart Brody, RagnarPreut, Kerstin Schommer, Thomas H. Schürmeyer).

CONCLUSION

As is evident the fact that stress causes wear and tear of various body tissues, but is essential part of life up to a certain limit. Stress is psychosomatic disorder originated by many causes and further develops many diseases and disorders like Diabetes. When this stress becomes the part of life individual it needs to be managed. Various methods including Yoga and Meditation are helpful in such conditions. Principles of sadvritta, aachararasaayan, dincharya, rituchara aims at prevention of stressful conditions. As for the herbs when we screen the various Mahakashaya mentioned in Charaka Samhita, few of the groups like Vayasthapana and Hridya Mahakashaya gains attention.

Hridya group of drugs are amla rasa pradhan and are rich source of vitamin c. in various studies vitamin c is proved to be Avery potent antioxidant as well as a good stress buster. Thus hridya drugs act on mind and helps in prevention as well as treatment of stress related disorders.

Drugs of Vayasthapan mahakashaya are considered to have antiaging properties. These are potent antioxidants and counters the ill effects of free radicals generated due to stress.

Thus we find that in Ayurveda stress and its related disorder diabetes can be managed at various levels effectively.

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